

NDAC/LO/030

1983 Nov 25

WP8100: Double Stars (Definition)

by L Lindegren

1. Principles

The Double-Star Process is intended to distinguish and further analyse objects which are either a priori known to be multiple, or for which the satellite observations give a worse than expected fit to the normal single-star model. It consists of three stages, namely:

(I) Flagging: the goodness-of-fit is examined for all stellar objects in the Input Catalogue and those suspected of multiplicity are flagged (of the order of 10 - 20 %).

(II) Fitting alternative models: a sequence of object models (single star, binary, optical binary, ...) is tried and corresponding parameters and goodness-of-fit measures computed.

(III) Selecting the best model: the results of the different fits are compared and the 'best' model is chosen according to (ideally) objective and well-defined criteria. (Whether this can actually be achieved for all objects is uncertain.)

The Double-Star process is, at the present time, clearly not on the same level of definition as previous processes. This is apparently due mainly to three circumstances. Firstly, the range of possible object models is very wide, and it is hardly possible to define the useful subset until extensive simulations have been made of the detection and fitting sub-processes. Thus the important problem of model parametrization will have to be part of WP8200. Secondly, the rôle of a priori data is not at all clear, partly because the contents of the Input Catalogue in this respect are only vaguely defined, and partly because we do not know exactly how to use such data.

This again ought to be clarified during the development phase (WP8200). Thirdly, the analyses under (I) and (III) above are mostly statistical and may depend on properties of the real data which cannot be simulated, or perhaps even anticipated, before the actual processing starts. An interactive system with access to good statistical packages may be an important ingredient of the Double-Star process, which is consequently to some extent undefined up to the time of the actual processing.

2. Summary of I/O Data

The relevant Data Interface Descriptions are:

DID#	SOURCE	DATA INPUT TO THE DOUBLE-STAR PROCESS
38	Back-Substitution	• Step 3 residuals and GOF
39	Attitude Catalogue	• attitude angles (including accurate values of Ω , updated by the Set Solutions and PRS Solutions)
40	IDT Signal Cat.	• IDT Signal parameters and GOF
41	Location Estimator	• GOF for the single-star light curve
42	Set Solution	• GOF for the abscissa residuals
43	Star Catalogue	• astrometric and photometric parameters, multiplicity indicators
44	OTF Data	• smoothed real-time calibrations of modulation coeff. and phase shifts
DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM DOUBLE STARS
45	Double-Star Cat.	• results of model fits for flagged objects

3. Detection of Double Stars

3.1. Construction of a total GOF

We shall attempt to form a total GOF measure for a specific star (i) by combining residuals at all levels of the processing. This can only be done approximately, by assuming that the observations of this particular star are made relative to a "fixed system" built on all other observations, calibration data, etc.

The star is parametrized (under the single-star hypothesis, which we shall be testing) by the 5-vector of astrometric parameters $\underline{a}_i$. Thus, in a given set (j) the abscissa depends on $\underline{a}_i$ and a number of "system" parameters (RGC pole, time, ephemerides, ...); but since $\underline{a}_i$ are the only "free" parameters we write $v_j(\underline{a}_i)$. In a frame (k) belonging to the set, the grid coordinate of the star at frame mid-time is similarly written $G_k(v_j(\underline{a}_i))$, although it depends also on "system" parameters such as attitude angles and LSD. The grid coordinate specifies uniquely the phase (β_{3k}) of the first harmonic of the light modulation, but not the remaining components of the 5-vector $\underline{\beta}_k$. These are determined either by the OTF calibration (β_{4k} and β_{5k}) or by photometric data (B_k, I_{ok}), which we allow to be free parameters in each frame. Thus we write $\underline{\beta}_k(B_k, I_{ok}, G_k(v_j(\underline{a}_i)))$. The IDT signal parameters $\underline{\beta}_k$ and the SSD finally determine the expected number of counts in each sample (ℓ). The complete model for the Poisson process, written in terms of all the "free" parameters, is then

$$E(N_\ell) = I_\ell(\underline{\beta}_k(B_k, I_{ok}, G_k(v_j(\underline{a}_i)))) \quad (1)$$

Each level of parentheses in (1) corresponds to a constraint on the permissible space of estimated intensities $\{\hat{I}_\ell\}$, given the observed counts $\{N_\ell\}$, thus reducing its dimension and increasing the residuals (and the GOF). At the first level of individual samples, our "model" reads $E(N_\ell) = I_\ell$ and the obvious solution is $\hat{I}_\ell = N_\ell$. We associate this estimate with $GOF = 0$ and $DOF = 0$, since the number of observations, $\dim\{N_\ell\}$,

equals the number of estimated parameters, $\dim\{\hat{I}_\ell\}$. At the next level, corresponding to the IDT Preprocessing, we introduce $NACC_k - 5$ constraints on each frame, by forcing the estimated intensities to obey the models $\hat{I}_\ell = I_\ell(\hat{\beta}_k)$. Thus $DOF = \sum_k (NACC_k - 5)$, where $NACC_k$ is the number of accepted samples on the star in frame k . Also $GOF = \sum_k \Lambda_k^0$, if Λ_k^0 is the dispersion of counts about the ML solution represented by $\hat{\beta}_k$:

$$\Lambda_k^0 = \sum_{\ell \in k, i} \frac{[N_\ell - I_\ell(\hat{\beta}_k)]^2}{I_\ell(\hat{\beta}_k)} \quad (2)$$

The next level (Location Estimator) constrains the estimates to be compatible with the calibration $(\tilde{\beta}_k, \underline{G}_k)$, increasing GOF by

$$\Lambda_k^1 = (\underline{\beta}_k^* - \hat{\beta}_k)' \underline{\Phi}_k (\underline{\beta}_k^* - \hat{\beta}_k) + (\underline{\beta}_k^* - \tilde{\beta}_k)' \underline{G}_k^{-1} (\underline{\beta}_k^* - \tilde{\beta}_k) \quad (3)$$

per frame and adding 2 DOF per frame. Going to the next level corresponds to the Set Solution and constrains the grid coordinates G_k to be compatible with a single abscissa per set; this adds

$$\Lambda_j^2 = \sum_{k \in j, i} \Delta G_k^2 / [(\underline{\Phi}_k + \underline{G}_k^{-1})^{-1}]_{33} \quad (4)$$

per set to the GOF, ΔG_k being the residuals of the Set Solution, and increases DOF correspondingly. At the last level (Step 2/3) the different abscissae are also constrained to be compatible with a unique 5-vector $\underline{a}_i$, increasing GOF by

$$\Lambda_i^3 = \sum_{j \in i} \Delta u_j^2 / \sigma_{uj}^2 \quad (5)$$

as function of the Step 2/3 residuals. The final expression for the total GOF for star i is then

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{GOF}_i &= \Lambda_i^0 + \Lambda_i^1 + \Lambda_i^2 + \Lambda_i^3 \\
&= \sum_{k \in i} (\Lambda_k^0 + \Lambda_k^1) + \sum_{j \in i} \Lambda_j^2 + \Lambda_i^3 \\
&= \sum_{j \in i} \left\{ \sum_{k \in j, i} \left[\Lambda_k^0 + (\beta_k^* - \hat{\beta}_k)' \Phi_k (\beta_k^* - \hat{\beta}_k) + \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + (\beta_k^* - \tilde{\beta}_k)' G_k^{-1} (\beta_k^* - \tilde{\beta}_k) + \Delta G_k^2 / \sigma_{Gk}^2 \right] + \Delta v_j^2 / \sigma_{vj}^2 \right\} \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{DOF}_i &= \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{total number} \\ \text{of samples} \end{array} \right) - 2 \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{number of} \\ \text{frames} \end{array} \right) - 5 \\
&= \sum_{k \in i} (\text{NACC}_k - 2) - 5 \quad (7)
\end{aligned}$$

An alternative form for Λ_k^0 might be the following:

$$\Lambda_k^0 = 2 \sum_{\ell \in k, i} \left\{ N_\ell \ln(N_\ell) - N_\ell - \left[N_\ell \ln[I_\ell(\hat{\beta}_k)] - I_\ell(\hat{\beta}_k) \right] \right\} \quad (2')$$

This is $-2 \ln[(\text{likelihood of } \hat{I}_\ell = I_\ell(\hat{\beta}_k)) / (\text{likelihood of } \hat{I}_\ell = N_\ell)]$, which from a general theorem is known to be asymptotically χ^2 distributed with $\text{NACC}_k - 5$ d.o.f. The two forms (2) and (2') are asymptotically equivalent for large count rates, as can be seen by expanding $\ln(N_\ell)$ in (2') as a power series in $(N_\ell - I_\ell) / I_\ell$:

$$(2') = \sum_{\ell} \frac{(N_\ell - I_\ell)^2}{I_\ell} - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{\ell} \frac{(N_\ell - I_\ell)^3}{I_\ell^2} + \dots \quad (8)$$

One reason for preferring this alternative form would be that it is actually minimized by the ML estimate $\hat{\beta}_k$, whereas (2) is not. This is however not really relevant, since we use a

second-order Taylor approximation of the likelihood function (2') in the vicinity of $\hat{\beta}_k$; the non-negativity of $\hat{\phi}_k$ and $\hat{G}_k$ thus guarantees $\Lambda_k^1 \geq 0$ in (3). More important considerations when choosing between (2) and (2') may be: ease of computation [(2) preferred], actual distribution at small count rates [(2) is probably closer to a χ^2 distribution], accommodation of outliers [the logarithmic loss in (2') is softer than the quadratic function in (2) when it comes to spurious high counts].

3.2. Flagging disturbed stars

Under the null hypothesis (that i is single) we ideally expect GOF_i to be χ^2 distributed with DOF_i degrees of freedom. In reality the distribution may be rather different, owing to the several simplifying assumptions underlying (6) and (7). We propose to make a semi-empirical determination of the actual distribution and its dependence on variables such as DOF_i , stellar magnitude, etc. The way to proceed could be roughly as follows.

From the way we have defined the GOF, it is reasonable to assume a fairly narrow, quasi-normal distribution under the single-star hypothesis. It is however strongly contaminated by disturbed (double) stars, for which we almost certainly get an increased GOF. The real distribution will thus consist of a gaussian kernel containing perhaps 80 - 90 % of the stars with remaining stars in a very extended tail towards high GOF values. The location and width of the gaussian kernel will however depend on DOF_i and possibly several other variables. The first problem will be to single out the principal factors determining the kernel distribution. This can be done e.g. by Principal Component Analysis with suitable precautions against the outliers (high tail). The stars are then grouped according to the principal components; if possible there should be several hundred stars in each group. The distribution parameters can now be estimated separately for each group, using e.g. probability plots or other robust methods based on the ordered sample. Finally the functional relations between the essential variables and distribution parameters are derived.

This allows to derive the required probability distributions under the null hypothesis (H_0) and parametrized by the essential variables:

$$f(x) = \Pr[\text{GOF}_i \geq x \mid H_0, \text{DOF}_i, \text{mag}_i, \dots] \quad (9)$$

The star is flagged as disturbed if $f(\text{GOF}_i) < f_0$. [We should consider the possibility to give $f(\text{GOF}_i)$ in the Output Catalogue as an "absolute" measure of goodness-of-fit.]

The statistical analysis described here is probably best done with the use of interactive graphical methods. This should not present a problem, as we have only a handful of variables for each of the 100,000 stars.

It can be noted that the selection of PRS stars can use very similar methods, i.e. rejecting candidates with $f(\text{GOF}_i)$ below some conservative level. As the GOF_i and DOF_i have to be computed before Step 2/3, they will not include Λ_i^3 in (6).

3.3. Detection

Rejection of the single-star hypothesis (flagging) is however not sufficient for proper detection of a double (or multiple) star. It is also necessary to demonstrate that the alternative hypothesis ($i = \text{multiple}$) gives a significantly better fit to the observations. The flagged stars are thus further analysed in relation to various multiple-star models. For this purpose a different definition of GOF is required; this is the topic of Section 4.2 below.

4. Processing of Flagged Objects

4.1. Rectified signal parameters

Once the suspected multiple stars have been identified, i.e. flagged, a finer analysis of individual FOV crossings will be required. Each FOV crossing (usually 8 or 9 consecutive frames) is a natural "unit of observation" for this purpose, since the geometry of any object with respect to the grid orientation will remain essentially constant over a full crossing. (The same is approximately true of the veiling glare effect, so that we can try to eliminate that in the same process.)

A crossing will be characterized by a set of "rectified" signal parameters, obtained by averaging the results of individual frames ($\hat{\beta}_k$) after calibration. The latter term here refers to elimination of all known variations and local effects, such as field-dependent modulation coefficients, phase shifts and attitude errors; in addition, the modulation phase is put on an "absolute" basis by being referred directly to an absolutely known point on the sky, the reference point P_i . This may be defined e.g. by the nominal astrometric parameters of star i as given in the Input Catalogue.

For the frame k we calculate the grid coordinate of P_i , $G_{ik}^{(P)}$, according to the usual formulae. In doing so, it may be convenient to avoid the mean abscissa $\bar{v}_{ij}$ as an intermediary datum by including the set zero point correction (c_j) in the a posteriori attitude. The attitude argument to be used is then

$$\omega_k := \omega_k + \psi_k + (\underline{r}'\underline{z})c_j \quad (10)$$

where ψ_k is the correction from the Set Solution and we have used that $\partial\eta/\partial v = \underline{r}'\underline{z}$ for $\zeta = 0$. Given the IDT signal parameters $\hat{\beta}_k$ for a FOV crossing $\kappa = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n\}$ we can now define a rectified parameter vector $\underline{b}_\kappa$ as follows:

$$b_{1k} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k \in \kappa} \hat{\beta}_{1k} \quad (11a)$$

$$b_{2k} + i b_{3k} = \frac{M_1^O}{n} \sum_{k \in \kappa} \frac{\hat{\beta}_{2k}}{\tilde{M}_{1k}} \exp[-i(\hat{\beta}_{3k} - 2\pi G_{ik}^{(P)})] \quad (11b)$$

$$b_{4k} + i b_{5k} = \frac{M_2^O}{n} \sum_{k \in \kappa} \frac{\hat{\beta}_{2k}}{\tilde{M}_{1k}} \frac{\hat{\beta}_{4k} + i \hat{\beta}_{5k}}{\tilde{\beta}_{4k} + i \tilde{\beta}_{5k}} \exp[-2i(\hat{\beta}_{3k} - 2\pi G_{ik}^{(P)})] \quad (11c)$$

Here M_1^O and M_2^O are nominal modulation coefficients (constant for the whole mission) and $\tilde{M}_{1k}$, $\tilde{\beta}_{4k}$, and $\tilde{\beta}_{5k}$ calibration values for the individual frames.

The significance of b_k can be understood as follows. Suppose that we have a point source of intensity I_s offset by an angle $\Delta\eta$ from P_i in the direction of scanning. If the response of the instrument is correctly described by the calibration values, we shall have the intensity at frame mid-time,

$$I_k = B + I_s + \tilde{M}_{1k} I_s \left[\cos(2\pi G_{ik}^{(P)} + \phi) + \tilde{\beta}_{4k} \cos(4\pi G_{ik}^{(P)} + 2\phi) + \tilde{\beta}_{5k} \sin(4\pi G_{ik}^{(P)} + 2\phi) \right] \quad (12)$$

with $\phi = (2\pi/s)\Delta\eta$. From the IDT Preprocessing we expect to find the signal parameters $\hat{\beta}_k = (B + I_s, \tilde{M}_{1k} I_s, 2\pi G_{ik}^{(P)} + \phi \pmod{2\pi}, \tilde{\beta}_{4k}, \tilde{\beta}_{5k})$, which upon rectification become

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= B + I_s \\ b_2 &= M_1^O I_s \cos \phi, & b_3 &= -M_1^O I_s \sin \phi \\ b_4 &= M_2^O I_s \cos 2\phi, & b_5 &= -M_2^O I_s \sin 2\phi \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

independent of k . For an object consisting of several point sources, the corresponding b -vectors are simply added (except for the background, B).

4.2. Goodness-of-fit statistic

The covariance of $\underline{b}_k$, $\underline{C}_{b_k}$, can in principle be calculated from the matrices $\underline{\Phi}_k$ and the uncertainties of the OTF calibration and attitude (the latter affecting $G_{ik}^{(P)}$). As we do not know, for instance, the correlation of OTF errors at different points of the field, the real calculation of $\underline{C}_{b_k}$ will probably be somewhat schematic.

The object model (Section 4.3) will permit to calculate the rectified vectors $\underline{b}_k^{(calc)}$ as functions of the model parameters. The goodness-of-fit statistic to be minimized is

$$\Lambda_i = \sum_k \Delta \underline{b}_k' \underline{C}_{b_k}^{-1} \Delta \underline{b}_k \quad (14)$$

with $\Delta \underline{b}_k = \underline{b}_k^{(obs)} - \underline{b}_k^{(calc)}$ and

$$\nu_i = (\sum_k 5) - (\text{number of object parameters}) \quad (15)$$

degrees of freedom.

4.3. Object models

An object consisting of M point sources (indexed $m = 1$ to M) will be characterized by several photometric and astrometric parameters.

Photometric parameters. In view of the variable background and photometric sensitivity of the instrument, it is probably necessary to take all B_k and I_{1k} as free parameters, where I_{1k} is the intensity of the first component in the crossing.

(Non-negativity constraints may however be imposed.) For the other components ($m > 1$) we can normally assume $I_{mk} = f_m I_{1k}$, with fixed ratios f_m to be determined. This gives a total of $2K + M - 1$ photometric parameters, if K is the number of crossings.

Astrometric parameters. These describe the offset of each component from P_i as function of time. Writing $a \equiv \Delta \alpha \cos \delta$,

$d \equiv \Delta\delta$, $\dot{a} \equiv \Delta\mu_\alpha \cos \delta$, $\dot{d} \equiv \Delta\mu_\delta$, $p \equiv \Delta\Pi$, where all differences are with respect to P_1 , we have different sets of free parameters depending on the object class:

Object class	Free parameters	Constrained parameters
single star	$a_1, d_1, \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_1, p_1$	-
binary with fixed comp.	$a_1, d_1, \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_1, p_1$ a_2, d_2	$\dot{a}_2 = \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_2 = \dot{d}_1, p_2 = p_1$
binary with linear motion	$a_1, d_1, \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_1, p_1$ $a_2, d_2, \dot{a}_2, \dot{d}_2$	$p_2 = p_1$
optical binary	$a_1, d_1, \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_1, p_1$ $a_2, d_2, \dot{a}_2, \dot{d}_2, p_2$	-
binary with curved motion	(special parameters)	-
triple star, fixed comp.	$a_1, d_1, \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_1, p_1$ a_2, d_2 a_3, d_3	$\dot{a}_3 = \dot{a}_2 = \dot{a}_1, \dot{d}_3 = \dot{d}_2 = \dot{d}_1$ $p_3 = p_2 = p_1$
etc.	...	...

For a binary with curved relative motions, the free parameters must be $a_c, d_c, \dot{a}_c, \dot{d}_c, p_c$ for the centre of mass, the mass ratio, and some parameters for the relative orbit. If only a small portion of the orbit is covered, the latter could perhaps define a polynomial for the position angle as function of time, $\theta(t)$, and the separation at mid-epoch (ρ_0); at other epochs the separation is then given by the law of areas: $\rho^2 \dot{\theta} = \text{constant}$.

4.4. Minimization problem

Let Ω_κ be the position angle of the +G axis across the object during FOV crossing κ , and let $a_m(t_\kappa), d_m(t_\kappa)$ be the positional offset of the m :th point source from P_1 at the time of crossing, according to the object model. The theoretical $\underline{b}$ -vector is

$$b_{1K} = B_K + \sum_m I_{mK} \quad (16a)$$

$$b_{2K} + i b_{3K} = M_1^O \sum_m I_{mK} \exp\left[-\frac{2\pi}{s}\{a(t_K) \sin \Omega_K + d(t_K) \cos \Omega_K\}\right] \quad (16b)$$

$$b_{4K} + i b_{5K} = M_2^O \sum_m I_{mK} \exp\left[-\frac{4\pi}{s}\{a(t_K) \sin \Omega_K + d(t_K) \cos \Omega_K\}\right] \quad (16c)$$

defining $\underline{b}^{(calc)}$ in (14) as function of the object parameters.

We have thus the standard problem of minimizing Λ_i with respect to the several object parameters. It is strongly non-linear and an infinite number of local minima can be expected at positional separations of about the grid period, s . For some of the parameters, especially the proper motions and parallaxes, the probable range is fortunately much less than s , so that a detailed grid search need only be done along certain axes of the multidimensional parameter space. Furthermore, the photometric parameters B_K and I_{1K} can probably be approximately eliminated at a local level (separately for each crossing), so that the global search is essentially limited to a_m , d_m and f_m .

A priori information on double stars is readily incorporated in the form of a vector $\tilde{\underline{w}}$ of object parameters with an associated covariance matrix $\tilde{\underline{C}}_w$; the functional to be minimized with respect to the vector $\underline{w}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_i + \Lambda_i^{(prior)} = & \sum_K [\underline{b}_K^{(obs)} - \underline{b}_K^{(calc)}(\underline{w})]' \underline{C}_{bK}^{-1} [\underline{b}_K^{(obs)} - \underline{b}_K^{(calc)}(\underline{w})] \\ & + (\underline{w} - \tilde{\underline{w}})' \tilde{\underline{C}}_w^{-1} (\underline{w} - \tilde{\underline{w}}) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

This will of course vastly simplify the minimization, in that the search region may be much more restricted.

The posterior covariance of the object parameters is obtained in the usual manner from the normal equations. Formally it can be identified with the inverse of $\frac{1}{2}(\partial^2 \Lambda / \partial \underline{w} \partial \underline{w}')$, but in reality this may have to be scaled according to the variance of the residuals.

4.5. Selecting the 'best' object model

Suppose we have tried fitting a series of object models, corresponding to the hypotheses

- H_0 : single star
- H_1 : binary with fixed relative positions
- H_2 : binary with linear relative motions
- H_3 : optical binary
- etc

and obtained estimates $\hat{w}_0, \hat{w}_1, \dots$ with goodness-of-fit statistics $\Lambda_{i0} \geq \Lambda_{i1} \geq \Lambda_{i2} \dots$ and $\nu_{i0} \geq \nu_{i1} \geq \nu_{i2} \dots$ degrees of freedom. In the end we shall have to select a single hypothesis and adopt the corresponding parameter vector as 'final'. Clearly an automated process is required, which can handle at least the larger part of the flagged objects.

For certain objects with a good prior classification, the choice may of course be trivial. But in general we shall have to rely on a combination of HIPPARCOS data and a priori information, possibly only of a statistical nature. It is easy to see that the simplest decision rules, ignoring prior information, are not sufficient. Consider for instance the F-test based merely on successive Λ_{in} and ν_{in} . This will always select the least complicated model giving a reasonable fit to the data. Thus, in the classification example above, it will prefer H_2 to H_3 if both hypotheses give about the same quality of fit. This happens irrespective of the estimation results $\hat{w}_2$ and $\hat{w}_3$. But in reality it may be that H_3 (optical binary) is by far the more likely case for certain combinations of parameters, e.g. a small parallax and large separation. The choice should then in some way depend on the estimation results. (From a different point of view one can of course argue that it should not be influenced by our prejudice about binary statistics. This seems to be a matter of policy which might be discussed in a wider context.)

A better decision rule could be to minimize some risk function such as the a posteriori expectation of the total

mean square error (mse) of some parameter(s), e.g. the parallax. The total mse considers not only the variance of the estimate, but also the bias, should the wrong hypothesis be selected. Its expectation when H_n is selected can be calculated as

$$E(\text{mse}_n) = \sum_{n'} \pi_{n'} \left[(\text{bias}|H_{n'}=\text{true})^2 + (\text{variance}|H_{n'}=\text{true}) \right] \quad (18)$$

where $\pi_{n'}$ is the posterior probability of $H_{n'}=\text{true}$. The $\pi_{n'}$ can be obtained from the prior probability (depending on $\underline{w}_{n'}$), combined with the likelihood of the estimate (from $\Lambda_{in'}$, $\nu_{in'}$) according to Bayes's theorem. The bias of $\hat{\underline{w}}_n$, given that $H_{n'}=\text{true}$, can be estimated simply as $\hat{\underline{w}}_n - \underline{w}_{n'}$ or taken to be 0 if $H_{n'} \subset H_n$ (i.e. if $H_{n'}$ is more restrictive than H_n).

Probably the selection process cannot be entirely automated for all objects. At any rate, the preliminary output catalogue produced by NDAC must give fits according to each model, in order to allow comparison with FAST results. It will also be valuable to keep double-star observations by HIPPARCOS in such a form as can be combined with future observations. The rectified signal parameters (with covariances) give a complete description of the observations in about 3000 reals per object.

5. Process Description

The Double Star process will consist of roughly the following subprocesses:

(i) During the (weekly) Location Estimations, accumulate $\Lambda_i^0 + \Lambda_i^1$ and $\sum_k \text{NACC}_k$ for every star, cf. (3), (6), (7).

(ii) During the Set Solutions, accumulate Λ_i^2 , cf. (4).

The results of (i) and (ii) are merged at suitable intervals for monitoring and the subsequent processing.

(iii) On (near-) completion of observations, a preliminary statistical analysis of $\Lambda_i^0 + \Lambda_i^1 + \Lambda_i^2$ and a priori multiplicity information will help to establish the final list of PRS stars.

(iv) After the final Step 2/3, Λ_i^3 is added to the GOF list, cf. (5).

(v) Statistical analysis of the complete GOF, $\Lambda_i = \Lambda_i^0 + \Lambda_i^1 + \Lambda_i^2 + \Lambda_i^3$ results in the final list of flagged objects as outlined in Section 3.2.

(vi) The complete chronological record of IDT signal parameters ($\hat{\beta}_{ik}$) is searched and rectified parameters calculated for all FOV crossings of flagged objects. The attitude (10) and the OTF calibrations are also input to this sub-process. The output, which shall have to be sorted after object number, is of the order of 200 Mb if 15 % of the objects are flagged (assuming 22 REAL*4 numbers per crossing for $\underline{b}_k$, $\underline{c}_{bk}$, t_k , and Ω_k).

(vii) Analysis of individual objects as in Section 4.2 - 4.5 and output of estimated object parameters etc.

DID 38		OUTPUT FROM : BACK-SUBSTITUTION INPUT TO : DOUBLE STARS				PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 83.07.05			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
ID	-	1. For each suspected <u>multiple star:</u> object identification number	-	0	9.10 ⁸	.0	1	-	8
NOBS	-	number of abscissa observations	-	0	999	0	1	-	3
ISET	j (p35)	1.1. For each abscissa observa- <u>tion (set):</u> set identification number	-	1	9.10 ⁵	-	1	-	6
TOBS	t _o +τ (p4)	mean time of observation ($\bar{t}_{ij}$)	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
RES3	$\Delta T_{ji} - \Delta \hat{T}_{ji}$	abscissa residual (p37)	rad	-10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	0	10 ⁻¹¹	-	7
SDABSC	σ_{ji} (p37)	standard deviation of abscissa	rad	-10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	0	10 ⁻¹¹	-	7
WEIGHT	-	weight factor (normally = 1)	-	0	10	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	6
ACOEFF(K), K=1,5	-	coefficient matrix for astrometric parameters (A_{ij})	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	0	-	10 ⁻⁶	6
ABSCPG	-	abscissa per grid period $\langle \partial u / \partial G \rangle_{ij}$	rad	0	10 ⁻⁵	-	10 ⁻¹¹	-	7

DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE		DEF	NUM ACC		DIG-ITS
				MIN	MAX		ABS	REL	
DID 40	OUTPUT FROM : IDT SIGNAL CATALOGUE INPUT TO : DOUBLE STARS PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 83.11.25								
IFRAME	-	1. For each frame: frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
NSTAR	-	number of objects in frame	-	0	10	0	1	-	2
ID	-	1.1. <u>FOR I = 1, NSTAR:</u> object identification number	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8
BMAG, BMV, SDBMV	-	magnitude, colour, s.d. of colour	mag	-2	15	99	10^{-2}	-	4
MULT	-	multiplicity information (TBD)	-	0	9999	0	1	-	4
IFIELD	$(-1)^f$ (p8)	field index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
ETAA, ZETAA	$\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}$ (p32)	approximate field coordinates	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
NACC, NREJ	-	no. of samples accepted/rejected	-	0	9000	0	1	-	4
GOF	-	goodness-of-fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
BETA(K), K=1,5	$\hat{\beta}$ (p29)	estimated signal parameters	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
CBETA(K,L), K=1,5; L=K,5	$\hat{\Phi}^{-1}$ (p29)	covariance of BETA(K) (or equivalent)	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6

D I D 4 1		OUTPUT FROM : LOCATION ESTIMATOR				PAGE : 1 OF 1	
DESIGNATION		INPUT TO : DOUBLE STARS				DATE : 83.11.25	
ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	DIG- ITS
	1. <u>For each frame:</u>						
IFRAME	frame identification number	-	1	9.10 ⁸	-	1	9
TMID	frame mid-time	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	15
NSTAR	number of objects in frame	-	0	10	0	1	2
	1.1. <u>For ISTAR = 1, NSTAR:</u>						
ID	object identification number	-	0	10 ⁸	0	1	8
GOFG	goodness of fit	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	-	6

D I D 4 2		OUTPUT FROM : SET SOLUTION				PAGE : 1 OF 1	
INPUT TO : DOUBLE STARS						DATE : 83.11.25	
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE MIN MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS
ID	i (p35)	1. <u>For each star in set:</u> object identification number	-	0 10 ⁸	0	1 -	8
ISSET	j (p35)	set identification number	-	1 9.10 ⁵	-	1 -	6
SDABSC	σ_{ji} (p37)	standard deviation of abscissa	rad	-10 ⁻⁵ 10 ⁻⁵	-	10 ⁻¹¹ -	7
GOFA	-	goodness of fit	-	-10 ³⁸ 10 ³⁸	-	- 10 ⁻⁶	6

D I D 43		OUTPUT FROM : STAR CATALOGUE				PAGE : 1 OF 1		
INPUT TO : DOUBLE STARS						DATE : 83.11.25		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	DIG- ITS
ID	i (p35)	1. <u>For each star:</u> object identification number	-	0	$9 \cdot 10^8$	0	-1	8
RAØ	α_o (p4)	Right Ascension at TEPOCH	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	12
DECØ	δ_o	Declination at TEPOCH	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-11}	12
PMRA	$\mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o$	Proper Motion in R.A. at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	-	10^{-19}	9
PMDEC	μ_δ (p4)	Proper Motion in Dec at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	-	10^{-19}	9
PX	$\tilde{\omega}$ (p4)	trigonometric parallax	rad	$-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0	10^{-11}	6
VR	v_R (p4)	Radial Velocity	m/s	-10^6	10^6	0	1	6
BMAG	-	blue (B) magnitude	mag	-2	15	99	10^{-2}	4
BMV, SDBMV	-	colour index (B-V) and s.d.	mag	-1	3	99	10^{-2}	4
MULT	-	multiplicity information (TBD)	-	0	9999	0	1	4
ICLASS	-	1.1. <u>multiplicity indicated:</u> object class	-	0	9999	0	1	4
WPRIØ	-	<u>a priori</u> parameter vector	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	6
CWPRIØ	-	covariance of WPRIØ	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	6

DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 83.11.25		
							NUM ACC ABS	REL DIG- ITS	
OTF(K), K=1,3	M ₁ etc (p12)	1. <u>For each frame and star:</u> OTF data interpolated to the relevant arguments	-	-1	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	6
COTF(K,L) K=1,3; L=K,3	-	covariance of OTF(K)	-	-1	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	6

D I D 4 5		OUTPUT FROM : DOUBLE STARS INPUT TO : DOUBLE-STAR CATALOGUE				PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 83.11.25		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS
ID	i (p35)	1. For each stellar object: object identification number	-	0	9.10 ⁸	0	1	8
MULT	-	multiplicity information (from IC)	-	0	9999	0	1	4
ICLASS	-	object class (from IC)	-	0	9999	0	1	4
PRSNGL	-	probability that the object is a single star (from GOF only)	-	0	1	0	10 ⁻⁶	6
JCLASS	-	1.1. If the star is flagged: a posteriori object model (1st choice)	-	0	9999	0	1	4
JCRIT	-	criterion for selecting JCLASS	-	0	9999	0	1	4
RISK	-	risk function (or similar)	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	-	6
WPOST	-	a posteriori parameter vector	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	-	6
CWPOST	-	covariance of WPOST	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	-	6
JCLASS	-	----- a posteriori object model (2nd choice)	-	0	9999	0	1	4
etc.		etc.						